

pathotype I and the antigen of pathotype II, and vice versa (see table). These results were confirmed by gel-diffusion tests.

In the gel-diffusion test with the antiserum of pathotype I, one to four precipitin bands were formed with nonheated antigenic preparations of pathotype I isolates collected at different sites; no band was formed against pathotype II antigen. With heated antigenic preparations, a thick precipitin band was formed near the antigenic well and two fast-moving precipitin lines

Agglutination titers of antisera of pathotype I and II isolates. Andhra Pradesh, India.

Group	Antiserum	Antigens	
		H.561	H.501
Pathotype I	H.561	1:5120	—
Pathotype II	H.501	—	1:2560

Serological reactions of heated (B) and nonheated (A) antigens of *X. c. pv. oryzae* isolates tested against pathotype I antiserum. The central well contained pathotype I antiserum. The outer well had non-heated (top) or heated (bottom) isolates of Punjab (1), West Bengal (2), Orissa (3), and Bihar (4, 5, and 6).

formed near the antiserum well, except with the antigen of pathotype II (see figure).

These results indicate that pathotypes I and II are serologically distinct in their antigenic components. □

TM4309: A blast (BI)-resistant, short-duration rice

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TM4309, a short-duration, high-yielding, BI-resistant, fine rice selection

from the pedigree of BAM3/ IR50, was selected to replace BI-susceptible IR50 in rabi season (Jan seeding). In dry (rabi) and early wet (kharif) seasons 1986-88, TM4309 had a yield average of 5.0 t/ha (see table). The lower yield of IR50 (3.9 t/ha) was due to severe damage by BI. □

TM4309 performance under BI stress at Tirur, India, 1986-89.

Season	Duration (d)	IR50			TM4309		
		Yield (t/ha)	Bl rating		Yield (t/ha)	Bl rating	
			Score ^a	Reaction ^b		Score ^a	Reaction ^b
Kharif 1986-87	105	2.9	9	S	4.1	1	R
Rabi 1986-87	105	3.6	9	S	4.9	2	R
Kharif 1987-88	110	5.6	5	MS	6.5	1	R
Rabi 1987-88	115	3.0	7	S	4.7	1	R
Kharif 1988-89	105	4.2	—	—	4.8	—	—
Mean	108	3.9	7.5	S	5.0	1.3	R

^a Standard evaluation system for rice. ^b R = resistant, S = susceptible, MS = moderately susceptible.

Reaction to sheath blight (ShB) disease of new rice cultivars in Andhra Pradesh (A.P.)

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We screened 38 rice cultivars developed at Agricultural Research Institute, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad — 18 short, 13 medium, and 7 long duration — against ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn. The cultivars and TN1 as susceptible check were grown in 1986 and 1987 monsoon seasons in a randomized complete block design with two replications.

Each entry was planted in 6-m² plots, at 15- × 15-cm spacing. At booting, individual hills were artificially inoculated by inserting pathogen grown

on typha bits between the tillers, just above the water. Disease intensity was evaluated 30 d after inoculation.

Differences between years were significant (Table 1), indicating the importance of measuring resistance across years. Varietal differences and their interaction with year were also significant. The highest incidence was on susceptible TN1 both years (Table 2). RNR6250, RNR74802, and RNR1535 had the lowest ShB incidence.

Table 1. ANOVA for ShB incidence in new rice cultivars. 1986 and 1987 wet seasons, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Source	df.	MSS
Replications within location	1	0.268
Years	1	135.148**
Varieties	38	2.655**
Varieties × years	38	2.953**
Error	76	0.287

** = significant at 1% level.